

MODERN APPROACHES TO PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS TO APPLY
PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATIONS

Sherniyazova Jamila Elmuratovna – doctoral student,
Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz
Email: jamiylasherniyazova@gmail.com
Tel: +99897 349 18 45

Abstract. The article examines modern approaches to preparing future teachers to apply pedagogical innovations in the educational process. The theoretical foundations are presented, and modern technologies and innovative strategies used in the system of professional training of teachers are analyzed. Special attention was paid to the digital educational environment, competency-based approach, individualization of learning, as well as foreign experience in teacher training.

Keywords: pedagogical innovations, teacher training, digital educational environment, competency-based approach, interactive technologies, innovative pedagogy.

The modern education system is characterized by the rapid implementation of digital technologies and innovative approaches, which is associated with globalization and the transition to a knowledge economy. The role of the teacher in these conditions changes significantly: he ceases to be merely a translator of knowledge, becoming a moderator of the educational process, an organizer of students' independent work, and a mentor capable of forming students' XXI century competencies.

Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan is on the path of innovative development aimed at radically renewing all spheres of state and public life. Because in today's rapidly developing era, the state that relies on new thoughts, new ideas, and innovations wins. President of our country Sh.M.Mirziyoyev also said: "Today, every teacher and educator, university professor should be able to apply the latest positive innovations in the field of education and science to the educational process, possess deep knowledge and worldview, in a word, be the most progressive representatives of our time and society".

As a result of globalization and the widespread use of information and communication technologies, the need arose to organize the educational process based on modern requirements. The role of the digital educational environment in the process of training future teachers is invaluable, as it provides an opportunity not only for obtaining knowledge, but also for independent learning, information processing, creative thinking, and the formation of innovative approaches.

In this regard, the training of future teachers should be oriented towards forming their readiness to use pedagogical innovations. This requires updating the content of pedagogical education, applying active and interactive methods, mastering digital technologies, and forming research and project competencies in future teachers. The relevance of the research is determined by the need to ensure the high quality of teacher training in the context of the digital transformation of education and the orientation towards the principles of sustainable development.

Pedagogical innovations are changes in the content and technology of education and upbringing, a set of actions aimed at increasing their effectiveness. The innovation process refers to the comprehensive activity of creating, developing, using, and disseminating innovations. Innovative processes are being introduced in our country in the following areas: the formation of new educational content, the development and implementation of new pedagogical technologies, and the creation of

new types of educational institutions.

Preparation of future teachers for the organization of teaching the fundamentals of science in educational institutions in their specialty based on new pedagogical technologies should be carried out comprehensively throughout their entire period of study at a higher educational institution. Pedagogical, psychological, philosophical, social, and methodological knowledge, as well as knowledge of technical means of education and information technologies, are acquired in the process of studying related disciplines.

Issues of the teacher's innovative activity are considered in the works of V.A. Slastenin, Yu.K. Babanskiy, I.F. Isayev, E.N. Shiyanov. They emphasize that innovations in pedagogy represent not only the introduction of new technologies but also changes in pedagogical thinking, culture, and methods of interaction with students. In foreign literature, much attention is paid to the concepts of constructivism (J. Dewey, J. Piaget), social learning (A. Bandura), and open education (T. Anderson). OECD and UNESCO researchers note that a modern educator must possess flexible skills (soft skills), digital literacy, and the ability to apply innovative approaches in diverse educational contexts.

The following methods were used in the work: Theoretical analysis of scientific literature on the problem of innovation in pedagogy; Comparative analysis of domestic and foreign experience in teacher training; The systematic approach considers teacher training as a comprehensive process that includes professional, methodological, and digital components.

Main directions and modern approaches

1. Competency-based approach in the training of future teachers.

The competency model of teacher training is aimed at forming not only knowledge but also skills, values, and experience in applying acquired knowledge in practical situations. The most important competencies are: Digital competence (ability to work with ICT, online environments, digital educational resources); Methodological competence (ability to design innovative lessons, apply active methods); Research competence (ability to analyze and implement pedagogical innovations).

2. Digital educational environment.

The digitalization of education determines the need for the integration of electronic platforms (Moodle, Google Classroom, Microsoft Teams), distance learning tools, virtual and augmented reality technologies, and artificial intelligence.

Future teachers must master the methodology of using: online courses and webinars; digital simulators and simulators; hybrid forms of learning (blended learning); knowledge assessment systems with elements of AI (adaptive testing).

3. Interactive teaching methods.

The use of interactive teaching methods ensures the active involvement of students in the educational process. Among the most effective methods are: Case method - analysis of pedagogical situations; Project activity - development of innovative pedagogical solutions; Business and role-playing games - modeling of the teacher's professional activity; Collaborative learning methods - group work, networked communities of teachers.

4. Foreign experience in teacher training.

In EU countries, the USA, Finland, special attention is paid to the development of pedagogical design, skills in working with digital educational technologies, as well as inclusive education. Training programs include: Mandatory courses on innovative pedagogical technologies; Practice using digital platforms; Formation of soft skills (communication, critical thinking, creativity). The

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Finnish model is aimed at developing research competencies: students are involved in pedagogical research, projects for the development of innovative methods.

5. Individualization and personalization of training.

The individualization of teacher training involves the use of adaptive learning systems, electronic portfolios, and personalized educational trajectories. This allows for consideration of each student's needs and level of preparedness, ensuring the formation of competencies at an individual pace.

6. Developing a teacher's innovative thinking.

A future teacher should be not only a user of innovations, but also their creator. For this, the following are important: Students' research activities; Participation in startup projects in the field of education; Creation of author's methods, digital products, educational applications.

Practical recommendations for universities

1. Include courses on innovative pedagogy and digital technologies in educational programs.
2. Organize virtual pedagogical practice using VR/AR.
3. Create pedagogical startup incubators for students.
4. Develop a project-oriented learning system.
5. Implement hybrid educational formats for teacher training.

Conclusion. Modern teacher training should be aimed at the comprehensive development of professional competencies, digital literacy, and innovative thinking. The introduction of pedagogical innovations requires systematic changes in the structure of pedagogical education: updating curricula, integrating digital technologies, active learning methods, and strengthening students' research activities.

In the future, the training of future educators will be built on hybrid learning models, the integration of artificial intelligence, and the creation of open educational ecosystems, which will allow for the formation of a new generation of educators capable of working in the context of a digital society and global changes.

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